

RESOLUTE
Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

Project number 777372

**WP8 – Knowledge integration
 and data management**

D8.7 Data Mining

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¹ Document, report

² Public, fully open

Publishable Summary

The main aim of this deliverable was to provide data mining support for priority ranking of SLC family members for target selection in WP4. Here we present KNIME workflows, which can be used to collect information which is available for SLCs in public databases. The first workflow automatically creates a presentation, which can be enriched manually and then be used to introduce the SLC of interest to the project consortium. The other workflows focus on potential assay strategies for SLCs.

Methods

Workflows to collect data on SLCs from public data sources were created with the KNIME Analytics platform. If available, a RESTful API was used to retrieve the data via the GET Request nodes. Where this was not possible, data files were downloaded and integrated into the workflow via corresponding Reader nodes.

As basis, the workflows use a list of all SLCs as compiled within the RESOLUTE project.

Workflow A - Automated SLC presentations for RESOLUTE target proposals

In this workflow, data from the following databases were used to automatically create a presentation:

- UniProt: names and alternative names of SLCs, protein function, subcellular localization, activity regulation, diseases
- COMPARTMENTS/UniProt: image of subcellular localization
- Gene Ontology: protein function
- IUPHAR/BPS Guide to Pharmacology: substrates
- ChEMBL: inhibitors (molecules with IC50 values).
- ProteomicsDB: tissue specificity

After downloading these specific data through GET Request Nodes in KNIME, the data was sorted through a report template in the Report Generation function, thus generating PowerPoint slides on the SLC of interest.

The workflow can be downloaded from the KNIME server, or executed on the KNIME webportal by entering the Uniprot accession number or the gene name of the SLC of interest. For the latter, the user can receive the generated presentation via email. Currently, we are also looking into the numbers of solute carriers that we can retrieve any information of.

Workflow B - Electrogenicity of transport reactions

To classify whether a transporter is electrogenic or not, transport reactions from the Gene Ontology (GO) database and the IUPHAR/BPS Guide to Pharmacology database (IUPHAR) were collected. For automated processing the KNIME analytics platform was used, however additional manual curation steps were necessary for the final result.

GO was queried via the QuickGO web services of the EBI for SLC UniProt Accession Numbers for molecular function data. With a subsequent API call the description of the GO terms was retrieved, and the text was filtered for the associated stoichiometric equations in the format Solute A(out) + Solute B(out) = Solute A(in) + Solute B(in).

Transport reactions from IUPHAR were not accessible through their API (April 2019), but were thankfully provided by the support team as CSV file. Following manual processing, the equations were in this standardized format: $a \text{ Solute A (in)} + b \text{ Solute B (in)}$, where a and b indicate the transport stoichiometry.

In the next step, the transport reactions are split to their individual fragments (molecules), which is necessary for the following analysis. For each molecule name (e.g. glutamate, Na^+) the workflow checks the PubChem database for the formal charge. The problem is that the workflow does not retrieve a formal charge for every molecule (e.g. the name could not be found), so a manual curation step is necessary. While PubChem returns the charges as implied with the name, we were assuming physiological conditions (pH 7,4). That has the consequence that e.g. amino acids were considered as dissociated.

For the calculation of electrogenicity the workflow needs to classify whether a molecule is transported into or out of the cell. That was solved by an extra parameter, +1 for a transport to the inner side of the membrane and -1 for a transport to the outside.

Workflow C - Assayability investigations

This workflow should give hints on how to assay a specific SLC. For this, information on available substrates is collected and compared with GPCR ligands. Electrogenicity predictions from Workflow B is added, as well as subcellular localization information.

IUPHAR transporter proteins with family IDs larger than 162 were used as queries for their substrates API call. The identified ligand IDs were used in a subsequent call to retrieve structures for the ligands. ChEMBL substrates were identified by querying the ChEMBL API for bioactivities for the list of UniProt IDs. Filters for substrates were the following: `standard_type` contains `Vmax` or `Km`, or the `activity_comment` field contains the word `substrate` (but not “not a substrate”). Substrates from the Bioparadigms SLC tables (<http://slc.bioparadigms.org/>) were collected manually in an Excel Spreadsheet, and read into the KNIME workflow with a corresponding reader node. DrugBank data was downloaded as XML file and imported with an XML reader node. The following filters were applied: compound action is substrate or protein type is Transporter or Carrier, unless the compound action is inhibitor or inducer.

Substrates from ChEMBL and IUPHAR were joined with GPCR ligands from ChEMBL and IUPHAR. From ChEMBL, data was retrieved for proteins classified as either GPCR family A, B, or C in the ChEMBL target classification. Applied filters were: `organism=Homo sapiens`; `activity_types: Ki, EC50, affinity or potency`; compounds were removed when the `activity_comment` field contained “not active”, “inactive”, “inconclusive” or “not determined”. From IUPHAR, all proteins classified as GPCR were used as query for the natural ligands. Molecule structures were converted to RDKit molecules before joining according to SMILES.

Subcellular Localization keywords were retrieved from UniProt (release 2019_02) and filtered for the most specific annotation terms within the “Cellular component” category. A predictor for cell surface proteins (SURFY, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30373828>) was used complementary to computationally discriminate cell surface SLCs from SLCs located in the membranes of intracellular compartments.

Results and Discussions

Workflow A is implemented on a KNIME Server instance running at the Pharmacoinformatics Research Group at the University of Vienna. RESOLUTE consortium members can access this workflow via a web interface, where they can enter the UniProt Accession Number or the gene name of the SLC of interest. After the execution of the workflow, the resulting presentation is sent via email or can be downloaded. Alternatively, the workflow can be downloaded to be run locally.

Comparing manually created presentations with the automated approach implemented in Workflow A showed that the manually created presentations contained more detailed information. However, the automated presentation could be used as starting point, where additional information known to the domain expert can be added.

Workflow B is able to calculate the electrogenicity of a transporter according to this example:

SLC1A1 transport reaction from GO: glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in)

charge transfer: $(-1) \times 1 + 1 \times 1 = 0$

SLC1A1 transport reaction from IUPHAR: 3 Na+(in) + 1 H+(in) + 1 glutamate(in) + 1 K+(out)

charge transfer: $3 \times 1 \times 1 + 1 \times 1 \times 1 + 1 \times (-1) \times 1 + 1 \times 1 \times (-1) = 2$

As the result of the calculation of GO is 0, SLC1A1 is classified as potentially electroneutral. The calculation of the IUPHAR example results in 2, in this case SLC1A1 is classified as electrogenic. A possible error source is that GO does not provide the exact amount of transported molecules, so a definite statement is not possible at this point. In contrast IUPHAR offers reaction equations with exactly defined stoichiometry, which helps to improve the discovery of electrogenic SLCs. But IUPHAR contains fewer reaction equations than GO, so we decided to include information from both sources. The workflow compares the results of both calculations at the end. If one variant suggests that a transporter is electrogenic, the SLC was classified as potentially electrogenic. The reason for this decision is the underlying use case, which should identify all SLCs where an assay based on electrogenicity would potentially be possible.

Workflow C found substrate information for 316 SLCs. Figure 1 shows how many SLC activities could potentially be measured with either electrogenicity assays or in a combination with GPCR assays. A comparison of the different data sources on substrate information shows that especially Bioparadigms and IUPHAR contain data which is not available in other data sources. This comparison only takes into account whether any substrate is mentioned for a given SLC, not if the listed substrates are identical.

Figure 1: Venn diagram of results from Workflow C. Diagrams were computed with http://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/cgi-bin/liste/Venn/calculate_venn.html

Conclusion

While the initial description of this deliverable focused on WP4, discussions at the first consortium meeting showed that such support is valuable for other work packages as well (especially investigations for possibilities to assay the transporter function for WP3 and 6). The data collected from public data sources is especially important at the initial stage of the project, to help decide which SLCs need more attention.